

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D9.4

Primary and Secondary Raw Material map (alpha version)

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
1RM/2RM	Primary raw materials / secondary raw materials
ARD	Analysis ready data
ASD	Analytical Spectral Devices
CLC	CORINE Land Cover
CORINE	Coordination of information on the environment
CRM	Critical raw material
EEA	European Environment Agency
EGDI	European Geological Data Infrastructure
EGS	EuroGeoSurveys
EO	Earth Observation
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
EU	European Union
JRC	Joint Research Center
PCA	Principal component analysis
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System
RockSL	Rock Spectral Library
SOM	Self-Organising Map
XRF	X-ray Fluorescence

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Within this task, we will develop two services: one specific for the Terravision mining sites and one at the EU level. The aim of both tasks is to visualise potential material stocks in Europe based on satellite data. In this report, we describe the methodology developed for the alpha version of the service.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The objective of the service ‘primary and secondary raw material maps’ is to develop maps which visualise potential material stocks in near real-time. This will be done on the one hand for primary raw materials in active mining areas and, on the other hand, for secondary raw materials in both active and closed (known) mining areas. This will provide information on the potential of material stocks in Europe.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

A workflow for primary and secondary raw material maps is developed, involving a combination between EO systems and in-situ data. This workflow includes pre-processing of remote sensing data, processing of remote sensing data, image classification, and data integration.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The outcome of the first 18 months period is a workflow describing the approach that will be followed when generating the primary and secondary raw materials maps as a service and as outcome of the Terravision project.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- An overview of the work done
- Description of the workflow to generate primary and secondary raw materials map

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable provides an overview of the status of the alpha version of the service 'primary and secondary raw material maps'.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to describe the workflow of the alpha version of the primary and secondary raw material maps for one of the Terravision demonstrator sites. The objective is partly achieved, but there is a slight delay in the development of the combination of satellite data with airborne data. This is due to a delay in the delivery of pre-processed airborne data, as well as ongoing validation of these data. Validation is based on heuristics as well as on in-situ ASD data, however, there is a delay of a few months in the delivery of the ASD results.

1.3 Intended Audience

The intended audience for this deliverable includes the leaders of the tasks whose output defines the service 'primary and secondary raw materials maps'. This deliverable ensures that the participants of the project have a good understanding of the service that will be developed, both for participants that play a role upstream (data providers) and downstream (users of the developed service).

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable begins with an introduction that provides a brief overview of the context of Task 9.4. The section "Primary and secondary raw material maps" describes the methodology and results of the service, which develops an alpha version of the primary and secondary raw material maps. Finally, the "Next steps" section summarises the main achievements and the next steps.

2. Primary and secondary raw material maps

2.1 Objective

Mineral exploration phases are conducted by mining industries to find economically and technically viable ore deposits. This exploration phase is one of the most relevant but also most costly, in terms of average investment return rate. This is especially the case if large areas are assessed, as a significant part of the work includes collecting field data, such as geophysical, geological, and geochemical data. This data variety contributes to the accuracy of the exploration campaign. As a result, various mining studies are currently combining field data (in-situ data) with remote sensing datasets, since the latter are low-cost and can play an essential role in identifying areas with a high mineral exploration potential [1].

The objective of the service ‘primary and secondary raw material maps’ is to develop maps which visualise potential material stocks in near real-time. This will be done on the one hand for primary raw materials in active mining areas and, on the other hand, for secondary raw materials in both active and closed (known) mining areas. This will provide information on the potential of material stocks in Europe.

Within this task, we will develop two services: one specifically for the Terravision demonstrator mining sites, and one at the EU level. The approach followed for these services is visualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Schematic overview of task 9.4

2.2 Primary raw material maps

2.2.1 Introduction

The primary raw material maps, developed for the Terravision demonstrator sites, will show the mineral types that can be distinguished using satellite data. Since Sentinel-2 has a global revisit time of five days, the Sentinel-2-based information on the map can be updated every five days. This information will be complemented with airborne, ASD and XRF data, to validate and refine the satellite-based analysis. These measured data are then combined with a spectral library to allow the identification of different materials. The information resulting from this analysis will be cross-checked with the Terravision demonstrator sites. Figure 2 gives an overview of the data that could be integrated into the workflow.

Figure 2 – Schematic overview of building blocks for the primary and secondary raw material maps.

The use of remote sensing data for mineral exploration has two main limitations: the presence of dense vegetation and the lack of depth penetration. Therefore, the maps generated will only provide information regarding the observable materials at the surface. When sub-surface information is available (in-situ data, including geochemical data), it can be combined using geostatistical methods, such as co-kriging, to generate maps that allow an estimation of sub-surface material availability. Co-kriging is an advanced geostatistical interpolation technique used to estimate the value of a primary variable (e.g., ore grade) at unsampled locations using both primary variables such as spatial data, and one or more secondary (auxiliary) variables that are correlated with the primary variable (e.g., geophysical data, geological information) [1]. Co-kriging thus correlates variables of interest to generate information covering unsampled areas, yielding an augmented materials map.

2.2.2 Approach to mapping a Terravision demonstrator site

The development of the primary raw material maps is based on the combination of the different building blocks, as shown in the UML activity diagram in Figure 3. First, when a primary raw material map is requested, it is checked against the CORINE and EGD habitat maps to verify that the region is a known mine. Second, data is gathered and pre-processed (in other Terravision tasks) to prepare for data analysis, for instance, by applying atmospheric corrections. Then, the remote sensing data is processed: feature extraction methods are

applied to the data to allow image classification in the next step. This will be explained in more detail further in this section (see Figure 6). Finally, other data types, such as geochemical data if they are available, are integrated with the processed satellite data to obtain comprehensive material maps. The following paragraphs will guide you through the approach and steps performed to come up with the alpha version of the primary raw materials map for the Canteras mining area.

Figure 3 - The workflow in a UML activity diagram.

First, Figure 4 gives an overview of the mining site (Source of the satellite image: Google Maps), including points of interest provided by the Canteras mining company. The second map (Figure 5) shows the polygon of the Canteras mining site based on the CORINE land cover map¹. This allows us to perform further analysis on specific mining areas. We have analysed these areas for mineral occurrences in two ways. In the first analysis, we use known band maths for the multispectral data from Sentinel-2 (T5.1).

Table 1 provides an overview of band maths for mineral detection with Sentinel-2 [2]. Figure 6 (left) shows the result of the calculation of the band ratio of ferric iron (band 4 / band 3). The intensity of the ferric iron reflectance increases from black to white, so we suspect more ferric iron where it is brighter/white. The occurrence of ferric iron could then be linked to other mineral occurrences, based on in-situ data.

The second analysis is based on unsupervised clustering (Windrim, Melkumyan, Murphy, Chlingaryan, & Leung, 2023). Figure 6 (right) was generated using the following three steps. First, the Sentinel-2 data for each mine of the CORINE map were downloaded using the code shown in Annex 1: Code Snippets Figure A1.1. Second, the multispectral data are processed using Sen2Cor to allow scene classification, atmospheric correction and conversion into Level-2A data. Third, the spectral features are analysed through an image classification approach using the Self-Organising Map (SOM) methodology. A SOM consists of neurons arranged in a

¹ <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover>

low-dimensional grid, where each neuron is connected to others through neighbourhood relations. The SOM methodology incorporates standard k-means clustering procedures to define a map of the area studied. An indicative code sample of this routine is shown in Annex 1: Code Snippets, Figures A1.2 and A1.3. The result is shown in Figure 6 (right).

Figure 4 – Overview of the Canteras mining site, including points of interest provided by the Canteras mining company. (Source of the satellite image: Google Maps).

Figure 5 - Polygon of the Canteras mining site based on the Corine land cover map.

Table 1 - The possible Sentinel-2 band ratios to detect minerals are limited to the features listed above of iron, carbonates, and silicates [2].

Feature	Sentinel-2 band math
Iron	
Ferric iron, Fe ³⁺	4/3
Ferrous iron, Fe ²⁺	12/8 + 3/4
Laterite	11/12
Gossan	11/4
Ferrous silicates	12/11
Ferric oxides	11/8
Silicates	
Alteration	11/12

Figure 6 – Primary raw materials map development – The Google satellite image (a) is overlaid with (b) the band ratio 4/3 showing the intensity of Ferric iron as seen through Sentinel-2 (more ferric iron gives a brighter image) and (c) the self-organizing map, using standard k-means clustering for 20 clusters.

To enable interpretation of these clusters, it is crucial to compare spectra of each generated cluster with known mineralogical spectral signatures. A spectral library will allow to make the link between spectral information and mineralogy, so that characteristic features can be identified. Busheng Xie et al. (2022) [3] developed an integrated open mineral spectral library (Rock Spectral Library, RockSL) which will be used in next phase of the project [3]. Alternatively, when ASD measurement results at the Terravision demonstrator sites are available in combination with mineralogical information, we will compare them with the clusters' spectral signatures.

The results are validated and augmented using site-specific analysis. These include hyperspectral airborne data and on-the-ground data through the ASD spectrometer campaign (T5.2) and XRF analysis of specific samples gathered on the mining area. During this phase of the project, the airborne data from a specific area of the Canteras mining site are being analysed. Figure 7 shows the application of the k-means clustering workflow on the airborne hyperspectral data. Note that the pixel colours of satellite and airborne data do not correlate with each other – the datasets have been clustered separately, but with the same source code. For combined clustering, the hyperspectral data should be reduced to the dimensions of multispectral data, which is not desirable as this implies a loss of information. The integration and comparison of satellite and airborne data were planned for the alpha version, however, as mentioned earlier, the airborne data have required more pre-processing than expected.

Figure 7 - Layered image of Google satellite (a), with k-means classification clustering of pixels coming from Sentinel-2 L2A (b) and airborne hyperspectral data (c), for 20 clusters. Note that the pixel colours of (b) and (c) do not correlate with each other.

Finally, to integrate and validate the data on imagery interpretation, VITO will use available information collected within the project, including geological, geophysical and geochemical. Potential primary raw material stocks will be visualised on a map in a format that can be used on the TERRAVISION platform. This will be done in the next phase of the project.

2.2.3 Upscaling

Once the methodology developed is proven and validated, it will be upscaled to the EU level. As a starting point for this scale-up, available databases at the EU level are being combined. These datasets, including the CORINE land cover map, the EGDI database (Jorgensen, Wittenberg, Deady, Kumelj, & Tulstrup, 2023), and the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS), provide information on mining activities in Europe. Combining these existing datasets will allow us to generate more insights regarding the information already available at the EU level. At a later stage of the project, after validation at the Terravision demonstrator site level, spectral information can be included as well. In the following paragraphs, the three currently included datasets are discussed, followed by a first glimpse of the results.

CORINE landcover map

The first CORINE Land Cover dataset ([link](#)) was released in 1990. Since then, it has become a cornerstone of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, managed by the European Environment Agency (EEA). Over the past 30+ years, it has provided vital data for understanding and managing land use across Europe.

Today, the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) product delivers a comprehensive land cover and land use inventory across Europe, using 44 thematic categories that include everything from extensive forests to specialised agricultural plots like vineyards. The latest full update of the dataset was completed in 2018. CLC supports a wide array of applications, from environmental assessment and urban planning to tracking climate change impacts and supporting disaster response efforts.

From this dataset, we isolated the polygons representing (closed and operational) mining sites in Europe. This adds up to 8731 polygons that have the mining site code 131.

EGDI dataset

The European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI; [link](#)) is a joint initiative designed to improve the accessibility, integration, and exchange of geological data across Europe. It acts as a centralised platform that consolidates geological information from a wide range of contributors, such as national geological surveys, academic institutions, and other relevant organisations.

The EGDI was initially launched in June 2016 with its first version and has since been expanded to incorporate additional datasets. In recent years, EuroGeoSurveys (EGS) has provided funding for the platform's operation and upkeep. EGDI is expected to act as a key entry point for Geological Survey Organizations to connect their data and digital tools to the European Plate Observing System (EPOS), once that platform becomes fully operational. Additionally,

geological data on raw materials from EGDI is accessible through the European Commission's Joint Research Centre Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) (see further).

From this database, we extracted the Pan-European mineral occurrence points. There are over 140.000 mineral occurrences and close to 60.000 mining sites (their status being in operation, abandoned, under construction,...) included in EGDI. At a later phase of the project, more information on geology/lithology/mining activities can be extracted and included in our combined dataset.

Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)

The Raw Materials Information System (RMIS; [link](#)) is a knowledge platform developed and maintained by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC). It serves as a centralised, user-friendly portal providing comprehensive information on raw materials essential for Europe's economy, industry, and environmental sustainability.

The RMIS supports the European Union's policies on raw materials, particularly those outlined in the EU Raw Materials Initiative and the Green Deal, by:

- Enhancing transparency and access to data on raw materials
- Supporting decision-making for policymakers, industry, and researchers
- Promoting sustainable resource management and a circular economy
- Monitoring the supply, demand, and criticality of raw materials

RMIS combines datasets from EU member states, industry, research institutions, and international sources, focusing on both primary (mined) and secondary (recycled) raw materials, including Critical Raw Materials (CRMs). Thematic areas include geology, supply chain, trade, demand, circular economy, environmental impact, governance, and social aspects. Finally, RMIS includes visualisation tools such as interactive charts, dashboards, and maps to explore and compare data. Finally, a policy interface contains tailored content to support EU strategies and initiatives like the Circular Economy Action Plan, Critical Raw Materials Act, and the EU Green Deal.

Information available at RMIS will be used in combination with CORINE and EGDI to validate available information on mining sites and minerals in Europe.

2.2.4 Results

The combination of available databases in Python has resulted in a detailed overview of delineated mining areas and mineral occurrences. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a satellite image of Greece, on which the CORINE polygons are plotted in blue and the EGDI mineral occurrences are plotted as red dots. Figure 8 zooms in on a mineral occurrence of nickel at (38.49055; 23.26338) latitude and longitude, respectively. In this way, geological information is combined with earth observation data. CORINE delineates the regions of interest for the collection of spectral data in the next phase.

Figure 9 - Example mining sites based on the Corine land cover, combined with mineral occurrence from EGDI.

Figure 8 - Zoom on a specific mineral occurrence at (38.49055;23.26338) latitude and longitude, respectively. The blue surfaces are polygons from the CORINE database, the red dot is a mineral occurrence as included in the EGDI database.

2.3 Secondary raw material map

While the primary raw materials map will provide an overview of the potential primary raw materials in European mines, the secondary raw materials maps will provide insights in the potential available amounts of secondary raw materials from mining waste.

Different types of mining waste can be distinguished based on where they originate during the mining process. This is schematically depicted in Figure 9. Within this project, we focus on the materials generated and stored at the mining sites, i.e., waste rock and tailings. Waste streams such as slags or other fractions, arising during the extraction of metals from concentrates, are excluded from the analysis.

Figure 9 – Schematic overview of the mining cycle and the occurrence of materials.

The secondary raw material map will be generated in analogy to the generation of the primary raw material maps. Also here, Sentinel-2 images will be combined with in-situ data (such as composition data of mining waste) where available.

In-situ data at EU scale will be collected through literature research. A valuable source will be the European FutuRaM project in which composition data of mining waste is gathered and made publicly available. This information will be combined with the database that were mentioned earlier related to the primary raw material maps (CORINE, EGDI, RMIS). This will allow a similar approach as the one followed for the primary raw materials map for Europe. Similarly, a clustering exercise can be done based on principal component analysis (PCA). This multivariate statistical technique is applied to enhance and separate spectral signatures from the background and to distinguish areas with the same spectra. This analysis is followed by an image classification technique. This technique is called the Self-Organising Map (SOM) methodology, resulting in a map providing insights into potential recoverable secondary raw materials from mining waste in Europe. The result will be visualised on a map in a format that can be used on the TERRAVISION platform.

3. Conclusion and next steps

In conclusion, progress has been made on both the primary and secondary raw material maps. At the Terravision demonstrator sites, a workflow has been generated to process Sentinel-2 data for the application of band math to assess ferric oxide presence and for the unsupervised clustering of pixels to identify clusters of spectral signatures. This workflow has been applied to the Canteras mining site. Simultaneously, the validation of airborne hyperspectral data is ongoing in collaboration with DIMAP. At the EU-level, existing datasets (EGDI, CORINE) have been combined to prepare for further data analysis.

To generate the primary raw material maps at the Terravision demonstrator sites, we will build on the results as discussed in the previous section. The validation of airborne data will be continued for future integration in the maps. The ENMAP hyperspectral data could be used as an additional spectral data source, for validation of the current dataset and for resolution improvement. Moreover, the spectral signatures of the Sentinel-2-based clusters (Figure 7) could be linked to materials using existing spectral libraries [3] and with in-situ ASD measurements and mineralogical knowledge.

As a next step, the in-situ data (ASD and XRF) should be integrated into these maps. This is done by augmenting the spectral library with site-specific information, as well as by plotting the in-situ data on the maps as points of interest.

An important aspect is the continuous validation of the maps with the Terravision demonstrator sites. While the maps could offer a visualisation and interpretation of the mining sites, the mining operators have experience and on-hand knowledge of the sites' features. Cross-checking the maps with their knowledge is crucial for validation and understanding.

Following up on the merging of the CORINE and EGDI databases, the linked information will be analysed. For instance, it will be investigated whether mineral occurrences are always linked to mining sites and vice versa. Other databases could be merged as well, to acquire additional information. For instance, information on secondary raw materials resulting from the FutuRaM project could be integrated.

The CORINE polygons delineate regions of interest for spectral analysis of mining sites. Two workflows will be evaluated. Firstly, spectral signatures similar to those on the Terravision sites will be searched for in the CORINE regions, as this could reveal straightforward parallels with the Terravision sites, for which more information is at hand. Secondly, one could investigate spectral similarities between mining sites with the same mineral occurrences. If these two workflows yield positive results, the next steps could investigate linking spectral information of the CORINE mining sites to materials using spectral libraries. As a result, one could obtain a map that identifies the potential of secondary raw material mining in the EU.

4. Bibliography

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5. Annexes

5.1 Annex 1: Code Snippets

```
from pathlib import Path
import json
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import shapely
import openeo
from openeo.extra.job_management import MultiBackendJobManager
import geography

# Functions #####
def prepare_jobs_df(
    grid_df,
) -> pd.DataFrame:
    """Prepare a DataFrame containing job configurations for
    benchmarking."""
    jobs = []

    for _, row in grid_df.iterrows():
        spatial_extent = shapely.to_geojson(row.geometry)
        jobs.append(
            {
                "spatial_extent": spatial_extent,
            }
        )

    return pd.DataFrame(jobs)

def start_job(
    row: pd.Series, connection: openeo.Connection, **kwargs
) -> openeo.BatchJob:
    """
    Start a new job using the specified row out of the jobs data
    base and connection.
    """

    # Get the variable parameters from the dataframe
    spatial_extent = json.loads(row["spatial_extent"])

    s2_cube = connection.load_collection(
        collection_id="SENTINEL2_L2A",
        spatial_extent=spatial_extent,
        temporal_extent=["2022-06-01", "2022-09-01"],
        bands=[
            "B01",
            "B02",
            "B03",
            "B04",
        ],
    )
```

```

        "B05",
        "B06",
        "B07",
        "B08",
        "B8A",
        "B09",
        "B11",
        "B12",
        "SCL",
    ],
    max_cloud_cover=25,
)

s2_cube.filter_spatial(spatial_extent)

return s2_cube.create_job(
    title="MultiBackendJobManager - Example",
    out_format="GTiff",
) # Generate a unique name for the tracker

# Workflow #####

# Load polygons of CORINE mines
filepath = "../data/U2018_CLC2018_V2020_20u1_EU27_mines.gpkg"
gdf_m = gpd.read_file(filepath)
gdf_m = geography.crs_transform(gdf_m, epsg="4326")
gdf_m = gdf_m.explode(column="geometry")
gdf_m = prepare_jobs_df(gdf_m)

# Initiate parallel download jobs
manager = MultiBackendJobManager(root_dir="../data/cdse/")
connection =
openeo.connect(url="openeo.dataspace.copernicus.eu").authenticate_
oidc(
    store_refresh_token=True
)
manager.add_backend("cdse", connection=connection,
parallel_jobs=2)

# Run the jobs
job_tracker = "eu27_mines.csv"
manager.run_jobs(df=gdf_m, start_job=start_job,
job_db=job_tracker)

```

Figure A1.1: Downloading Sentinel-2 L2A spectral images from the CDSE platform for CORINE mines in Europe.

```

from pathlib import Path
import re
import glob
import json
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd

```

```

import xarray as xr

from sklearn.decomposition import PCA
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

from terravision.src.config import CONFIG

# data location
rootfolderpath_data = Path(CONFIG.data_path) / "eu27_mines/job_j-
*"
folderpaths = glob.glob(str(rootfolderpath_data))
filepaths_img = glob.glob(folderpaths[0] + "/*.tif")

# translate between Sentinel-2 band indices in .tiff file and
their names
onehot_bands = {
    1: "B01",
    2: "B02",
    3: "B03",
    4: "B04",
    5: "B05",
    6: "B06",
    7: "B07",
    8: "B08",
    9: "B8A",
    10: "B09",
    11: "B11",
    12: "B12",
}

folderpath = folderpaths[0]
filepaths_img = glob.glob(folderpath + "/*.tif")
filepath_img = filepaths_img[0]

jobid = filepath_img.split("\\")[-2]
extracted_date = re.search(r"\d{4}-\d{2}-\d{2}",
filepath_img).group()

da = xr.load_dataset(filepath_img)
da = da.assign_coords({"date": [extracted_date], "jobid":
[jobid]})

# remove masked values
cube_scl = da.sel(band=13).band_data.values
mask = (
    (cube_scl == 2) # Dark Area Pixels
    | (cube_scl == 3) # Cloud Shadows
    | (cube_scl == 5) # Bare Soils
    | (cube_scl == 8) # Clouds medium probability
    | (cube_scl == 10) # Cirrus
).astype(bool)
df = pd.DataFrame(
    np.nan,
    columns=[

```

```

        "B01",
        "B02",
        "B03",
        "B04",
        "B05",
        "B06",
        "B07",
        "B08",
        "B8A",
        "B09",
        "B11",
        "B12",
        "jobid",
        "date",
    ],
    index=len(a.sel(band="B01").band_data.values),
    dtype=str,
)
for k, v in onehot_bands.items():
    cube_b = da.sel(band=k).band_data.values
    cube_b[~mask] = -9999
    df[v] = cube_b[cube_b != -9999].flatten().astype(float)

# apply principal component analysis (PCA)
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(df)
pca = PCA(n_components=2)
X_pca = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)
df_pca = pd.DataFrame(X_pca, columns=["PC1", "PC2"])

```

Figure A1.2: Perform principal component analysis of Sentinel-2 spectra as a preliminary cluster analysis step before K-means.

```

import pandas as pd
from osgeo import gdal
import numpy as np
import os
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
import rasterio

# Sentinel-2 L2A image downloaded from the CDSE platform
filepath = "../data/openEO_2022-06-07Z.tif"

with rasterio.open(filepath) as dataset:
    # Read first 3 bands of image
    image = dataset.read([1, 2, 3])
    # Rearrange dimensions to (height, width, channels)
    image = np.moveaxis(image, 0, -1)

pixels = image.reshape(-1, 3)

```

```

# K-means clustering
kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=20, random_state=0)
kmeans.fit(pixels)

# Get cluster labels
labels = kmeans.labels_
classified_image = labels.reshape(image.shape[:2])
classified_image = classified_image.astype(np.uint8)

# Create new raster
t = gdal.Open(filepath)
driver = gdal.GetDriverByName("GTiff")
options = ["COMPRESS=LZW"]
out_tif = "cl_20_kmeans.tif"
r = driver.Create(
    out_tif, t.RasterXSize, t.RasterYSize, 1, gdal.GDT_Int16,
    options=options
)

# Set metadata
r.SetGeoTransform(t.GetGeoTransform())
r.SetProjection(t.GetProjection())

# Save result
out_band = r.GetRasterBand(1)
out_band.WriteArray(classified_image)

```

Figure A1.3: K-means clustering of one CORINE mine downloaded with the previous code snippet (Fig. A1.2).